

Prescription compliance with National Formulary restrictions: Evaluation and information system–based strategies in an Indonesian tertiary hospital

Elmiawati Latifah¹, Muslim Hidayat², Sari Febriliani³, Ariska Yulaikah¹, Ananda Choirinisa Eka Putri¹, Salwa Sahiya Putri¹, Arini Khusnayain 'Azumah¹

¹ Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Health Science, Universitas Muhammadiyah Magelang, Magelang, Central Java, Indonesia

² Department of Informatics Management, Universitas Sains Al-Qur'an, Wonosobo, Central Java, Indonesia

³ Hospital Pharmacy Department, Soerojo Hospital, Magelang, Central Java, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Elmiawati Latifah (elmiawatilatifah@unimma.ac.id)

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Abstract

The National Formulary plays a critical role in promoting rational drug use and controlling healthcare costs within Indonesia's National Health Insurance system. Ensuring compliance with formulary restrictions, including prescriber authorization criteria, is essential to maintain prescribing quality, patient safety, and financial sustainability. However, evidence regarding compliance and system-level implementation challenges in tertiary hospital settings remains limited. This study aimed to evaluate prescribers' compliance with National Formulary restrictions, including prescriber authorization requirements, and to identify system-level barriers and potential digital-based improvement strategies in an Indonesian tertiary hospital. A mixed-methods case study was conducted in a Ministry of Health Class A tertiary hospital. The quantitative phase analyzed 16,725 outpatient prescriptions issued between January and July 2025, comprising 705 drug items subject to formulary restriction criteria. Compliance was assessed based on formulary inclusion and prescriber authorization requirements. The qualitative phase involved focus group discussions and in-depth interviews with physicians, pharmacists, information system personnel, and hospital administrators. Quantitative data were analyzed descriptively using Microsoft Excel, whereas qualitative data were analyzed using inductive thematic analysis supported by NVivo version 14. Overall compliance with National Formulary restrictions was high (98.4%), with only 11 of 705 drug items (1.56%) classified as noncompliant. Evaluation of prescriber authorization restrictions demonstrated an extremely high compliance rate, with only one drug item (0.14%), sildenafil, prescribed by a physician without the authorized specialty. Qualitative findings identified key system-level barriers, including limited integration of formulary information into electronic prescribing systems, reliance on individual clinician knowledge, lack of structured monitoring mechanisms, and absence of real-time formulary decision support. Recommended improvement strategies included strengthening digital formulary integration, implementing automated reminder systems, incorporating recommendatory clinical decision support features, and integrating formulary restriction information into physician dashboards. Compliance with National Formulary restrictions was very high, reflecting effective institutional governance and prescribing oversight. However, sustainable formulary compliance requires strengthening digital integration, automated monitoring, and clinical decision support systems. Integrating flexible, patient-centered digital formulary tools into routine prescribing workflows is essential to promote rational drug use, enhance medication safety, and support the long-term sustainability of Indonesia's National Health Insurance system.

Keywords

clinical decision support systems, National Formulary, prescriber authorization, prescribing compliance, rational drug use

Introduction

Rational drug use is a fundamental principle for ensuring the accuracy, safety, cost-effectiveness, and overall quality of healthcare services. It requires that medicines be prescribed according to appropriate clinical indications, supported by evidence, affordable, and consistent with patient safety standards (Sisay et al. 2017). However, irrational drug use remains a major challenge in many low- and middle-income countries, contributing to increased healthcare costs, reduced quality of care, treatment failure, and the acceleration of antimicrobial resistance (Park et al. 2017; World Health Organization 2021). These challenges underscore the importance of strengthening policy instruments and monitoring systems to promote rational prescribing practices and ensure the sustainable use of healthcare resources.

One of the key policy instruments for promoting rational medicine use is the National Formulary. In Indonesia, the government has established the National Formulary as the official list of medicines covered under the National Health Insurance scheme and as a regulatory tool to ensure medicine quality, clinical appropriateness, and cost control (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia 2024). Beyond listing approved medicines, the National Formulary defines specific restriction criteria governing their use, such as approved indications, patient eligibility criteria, and designated lines of therapy (Peacocke et al. 2022).

Evidence from international studies consistently demonstrates persistent gaps. Studies in Sierra Leone and Eastern Ethiopia reported excessive polypharmacy, high rates of antibiotic prescribing beyond World Health Organization (WHO) standards, and incomplete adherence to recommended prescribing indicators, despite improvements in generic prescribing and the use of essential medicines (Sisay et al. 2017; Cole and Routledge 2018; Ozawa et al. 2020; Mohammed and Faris 2021). These findings underscore the urgent need to strengthen monitoring systems and policy enforcement mechanisms to ensure rational medicine use and optimize healthcare resource utilization.

In Indonesia, hospitals participating in the National Health Insurance system are required to comply with the National Formulary, including its specific restrictions. A tertiary referral hospital under the Ministry of Health provides an important setting for evaluating compliance with National Formulary restrictions. This is particularly relevant in psychiatric services, where patients with chronic mental disorders often require complex pharmacotherapy involving antipsychotics, antidepressants, and mood stabilizers, many of which are subject to specific formulary restrictions related to indications, eligibility, and lines of

therapy. The clinical complexity of these cases may present challenges in balancing individualized patient care with formulary policy compliance, highlighting the need for effective monitoring and system-level support.

Previous studies in Indonesia have primarily focused on conformity with the National Formulary medicine list, with limited attention to compliance with specific formulary restriction criteria. Evaluating adherence to these restrictions is essential to ensure therapeutic appropriateness, maintain service quality, and support cost control within the National Health Insurance system. Furthermore, integrating formulary compliance monitoring with hospital information systems may enhance prescribing oversight, improve transparency, and facilitate more effective implementation of national pharmaceutical policies.

Accordingly, this study aims to evaluate prescription compliance with National Formulary restriction criteria and to explore information system based implementation strategies in a Class A tertiary hospital in Indonesia. By employing a mixed-methods approach, this study provides comprehensive insights into both compliance patterns and system-level factors influencing formulary adherence. The findings are expected to contribute empirical evidence to support policy improvement, strengthen quality assurance mechanisms, and enhance the efficiency and sustainability of the national health insurance system.

Methods

Study design and setting

This study employed a mixed-methods case study design conducted at a Class A tertiary referral hospital under the Ministry of Health of Indonesia, which serves as a national referral center. Ethical approval was obtained prior to data collection from the institutional ethics committee (Approval No. DP.04.03/D.XXXVI.12/44/2025). The study followed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods approach, consisting of a quantitative retrospective phase followed by a qualitative exploratory phase. This design enabled a comprehensive assessment of formulary compliance patterns and facilitated in-depth exploration of system-level factors influencing prescribing practices.

Quantitative phase

The quantitative phase employed a descriptive retrospective design to assess outpatient prescription compliance with the National Formulary and its associated restriction criteria. Prescription data were extracted from the hospital's electronic Hospital Management Information System.

A total of 16,725 outpatient prescription sheets, defined as individual prescribing encounters issued between January and July 2025, were included in the analysis. These prescription sheets contained 705 drug items that were evaluated for compliance.

Compliance with National Formulary restriction criteria was assessed based on two components: (1) formulary inclusion status and (2) adherence to applicable formulary restriction criteria. First, each prescribed medicine was evaluated to determine whether it was listed in the National Formulary. Second, compliance was assessed by cross-referencing drug item data with prescriber infor-

mation obtained from the hospital information system to verify whether the prescribing physician's specialty was consistent with the authorized prescriber restrictions defined in the National Formulary. Drug items were classified as compliant only if they were listed in the formulary and met all applicable restriction criteria.

Compliance was calculated using prescribed drug items as the unit of analysis. Each drug item was evaluated individually for formulary inclusion and restriction criteria compliance. Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel, and prescription compliance was calculated as a percentage using the following formula:

$$\text{Prescription compliance(\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of drug items compliant with Fornas restrictions}}{\text{Total number of prescribed drug items}} \times 100$$

Qualitative phase

The qualitative phase aimed to explore factors influencing prescribers' adherence to National Formulary restrictions. Purposive sampling was used to recruit key informants based on their direct involvement in prescribing, dispensing, or managing formulary implementation. Participants included specialist physicians, clinical pharmacists, and hospital management personnel responsible for pharmaceutical services and policy implementation. Two focus group discussions (FGDs), each consisting of eight participants, were conducted to facilitate interactive discussion and capture diverse perspectives. Participants were recruited using purposive sampling based on their direct involvement in prescribing, dispensing, or managing formulary implementation. Eligible participants included specialist physicians, clinical pharmacists, and hospital management personnel responsible for pharmaceutical services and policy implementation.

In addition, semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with selected key informants who held critical roles in formulary management or had extensive experience prescribing medicines subject to formulary restrictions. These interviews enabled deeper exploration of emerging themes and provided clarification and contextualization of findings from the FGDs. Participants were purposively selected to ensure representation across different clinical specialties, professional roles, and organizational responsibilities.

Participant recruitment and data collection were conducted concurrently and continued until data saturation was achieved, defined as the point at which no new themes, concepts, or relevant insights emerged from subsequent interviews and discussions. All FGDs and interviews were conducted face-to-face in a private setting and audio-recorded with participants' written informed consent. The use of multiple data sources and participant groups supported data triangulation and enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the qualitative findings.

Data analysis and trustworthiness

Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim and verified for accuracy by comparing the transcripts with the origi-

nal recordings prior to analysis. Data were analyzed using NVivo version 14 following an inductive thematic analysis approach, which enables systematic identification, organization, and interpretation of patterns within qualitative data (Braun and Clarke 2019; Byrne 2022). Two researchers independently conducted the initial coding to enhance analytical rigor and investigator triangulation, thereby improving the credibility and reliability of the findings (Nowell et al. 2017). Any discrepancies in coding were discussed and resolved through consensus to ensure consistency in interpretation.

The initial codes were then organized into categories, themes, and subthemes through an iterative and reflexive analytical process consistent with contemporary qualitative research standards. The resulting themes and subthemes were further reviewed, refined, and validated by additional members of the research team to ensure conceptual clarity and thematic coherence. All analytical procedures were systematically documented to establish an audit trail, thereby enhancing the dependability and confirmability of the findings.

Data triangulation was performed by cross-referencing qualitative findings with prescription records obtained from the hospital information system and by comparing perspectives across different participant groups, including specialist physicians, clinical pharmacists, and hospital management personnel. Triangulation strengthens the rigor and trustworthiness of qualitative findings by integrating multiple data sources and analytical perspectives. Final themes were reviewed and agreed upon by the entire research team to ensure the credibility, dependability, confirmability, and overall trustworthiness of the qualitative findings.

Results

Compliance with National Formulary restrictions

In the first phase of the study, secondary data were collected from outpatient prescription records to evaluate compliance with National Formulary restriction criteria.

Prescription data were extracted from the hospital information system for the period from January to July 2025. The analysis quantified formulary compliance and examined prescribing patterns, providing a comprehensive evaluation of formulary implementation in routine outpatient clinical practice.

Compliance with National Formulary restriction criteria was evaluated at the drug-item level, including assessment of prescribing authorization in accordance with formulary restriction requirements. During the study period, a total of 705 drug items were prescribed. Of these, 694 drug items (98.44%) were compliant with National Formulary restriction criteria, whereas 11 drug items (1.56%) were classified as noncompliant. This high level of compliance suggests effective formulary governance and strong integration of formulary policies into routine clinical prescribing workflows (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Compliance with National Formulary restriction criteria based on drug-item analysis.

Evaluation of prescriber authorization restrictions identified one restricted medicine, sildenafil, that was prescribed by a physician without the authorized specialty as specified in the National Formulary. This case accounted for 0.14% of the total prescribed drug items, indicating a very low level of noncompliance and demonstrating strong adherence to prescriber authorization requirements (Fig. 2).

Despite the high overall compliance rate, 11 of 705 prescribed drug items (1.56%) were identified as non-compliant with the National Formulary. These medicines

Figure 2. Compliance with prescriber authorization restrictions based on drug-item analysis.

were not listed in the National Formulary and are presented in Table 1. The non-formulary medicines included antihistamines, multivitamin supplements, anticonvulsants, antidepressants, mucolytics, pediatric nutritional products, and appetite stimulants. Noncompliant prescriptions represented a very small proportion of total prescribing during the study period, indicating that formulary deviations were infrequent. Furthermore, these medicines were distributed across multiple therapeutic classes, including neurological, psychiatric, respiratory, and nutritional agents (Table 1), suggesting that formulary noncompliance was not concentrated within a single clinical domain.

Table 2 presents the distribution of compliance with the National Formulary across outpatient services. Overall compliance was high, with 694 of 705 prescribed drug items (98.44%) conforming to National Formulary guidelines. The General Clinic achieved full compliance (100.00%), whereas the Neurology and Internal Medicine Clinics demonstrated compliance rates of 98.75% and 98.67%, respectively. The Psychiatry Clinic showed the lowest compliance rate (98.00%) and accounted for the highest number of noncompliant drug items. Although compliance rates exceeded 98% across all services, variations were observed between polyclinics. The Psychiatry Clinic recorded the highest number of noncompliant drug items ($n = 8$), followed by Internal Medicine ($n = 2$) and Neurology ($n = 1$), whereas the General Clinic achieved full compliance. These findings indicate consistently high formulary adherence across outpatient services, with only minor variations in compliance levels.

Table 1. Drug items not compliant with the National Formulary.

No	Medicine name	Dosage form	Description
1	Otede Tab (Diphenhydramine)	Tablet	Antihistamine, OTC
2	Curvit Syrup 60 ml	Syrup	Multivitamin supplement
3	Divalproex Sodium ER 250 mg	Extended-release tablet	Anticonvulsant/mood stabilizer
4	Brintellix 10 mg (Vortioxetine)	Tablet	Antidepressant
5	Halmezin Syr	Syrup	Respiratory therapy
6	Aloclair Plus Spray	Oral spray	Treatment for mouth ulcers / mucositis
7	Ambroxol 30 mg	Tablet	Mucolytic
8	Apialys 100 ml Drops	Oral drops	Pediatric vitamins and nutrition
9	Apisate (Diethylpropion HCl 75 mg)	Tablet	Anti-obesity medication (appetite suppressant)
10	Arcapec Tab	Tablet	Supplement
11	Aspilets Chewable	Chewable tablet	Analgesic-antipyretic

Table 2. Distribution of National Formulary compliance by type of service.

Polyclinic	Number of drug items	National Formulary compliant	Non- National Formulary compliant	Compliance (%)	Non-compliance
Psychiatry Clinic	400	392	8	98.00	2.00
Internal Medicine Clinic	150	148	2	98.67	1.33
Neurology Clinic	80	79	1	98.75	1.25
General Clinic	75	75	0	100.00	0.00
Total	705	694	11	98.44	1.56

Factors influencing compliance with National Formulary restrictions

The second phase of this study employed a qualitative approach to explore factors influencing prescribers' compliance with National Formulary restrictions. This approach was used to gain an in-depth understanding of healthcare professionals' perceptions, experiences, and challenges related to the implementation of formulary-based drug restriction policies. Analysis of the qualitative data revealed that limitations in hospital drug management constituted a key factor influencing compliance with National Formulary restrictions. Qualitative analysis revealed that system-level and technological factors played a central role in influencing formulary compliance. Several interrelated issues were identified, including the absence of integrated formulary information systems, dependence on pharmacists' individual knowledge, limited information technology infrastructure, and lack of formal monitoring and evaluation systems. These findings indicate that formulary compliance was primarily achieved through manual processes rather than automated digital support, highlighting potential vulnerabilities in sustaining compliance as service demand increases.

These limitations were reported to affect prescribers' adherence both directly and indirectly. Several interrelated issues were identified, including the absence of an integrated information system for National Formulary restrictions, dependence on pharmacists' individual memory to apply restriction rules, limited information technology (IT) resources, and the lack of formally documented monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Collectively, these factors contributed to inconsistencies in the application of formulary restrictions during the prescribing process.

The relationships among these factors were visualized using NVivo version 14, which generated a project map illustrating the key limitations in hospital drug management (Fig. 3). The NVivo-generated project map (Fig. 3) illustrates the interaction between system limitations, human factors, and technological constraints, demonstrating that digital infrastructure plays a critical role in enabling consistent formulary adherence.

Strategies to enhance the implementation of National Formulary restrictions

Qualitative analysis, as visualized in the project map generated using NVivo version 14 (Fig. 4), identified several

Figure 4. Project map of strategies to enhance the implementation of National Formulary restrictions.

key strategies to strengthen the implementation of National Formulary restrictions in hospital settings. These strategies emphasize the importance of enhancing technological infrastructure, information system integration, and clinical orientation in the application of formulary policies.

Participants emphasized that integration of formulary data into electronic prescribing systems is essential to ensure real-time validation of prescriptions. Automated reminder systems were identified as a key strategy to alert prescribers when non-formulary medicines are selected. Participants also highlighted the importance of recommendatory (non-locking) clinical decision support systems, which allow prescribers to retain clinical autonomy while ensuring appropriate documentation and monitoring of formulary deviations. Integration of formulary information into physician dashboards was identified as an effective strategy to improve prescribing transparency and facilitate real-time compliance monitoring. Overall, these findings demonstrate that sustainable formulary compliance requires a combination of regulatory enforcement,

digital infrastructure integration, clinical decision support tools, and ongoing professional training.

In addition, the project map highlighted the importance of capacity-building initiatives, including targeted training programs for healthcare providers and strengthened communication channels between pharmacists and physicians, to support consistent implementation of formulary policies. Overall, the findings suggest that improving compliance with National Formulary restrictions depends not only on regulatory enforcement but also on system readiness, flexible implementation mechanisms, and the effective use of digital technologies to support routine clinical practice.

Discussion

Key findings of the study

The findings of this study carry important implications for both public health practice and health professional education, particularly in strengthening rational drug use within national health insurance systems. At the public health level, the high compliance with National Formulary restrictions observed in this study demonstrates the effectiveness of formulary policies as instruments for cost containment, quality assurance, and medication safety when supported by strong institutional governance and structured implementation frameworks (Wirtz et al. 2017; Peacocke et al. 2022). Formulary systems play a central role in promoting rational medicine use and ensuring equitable access to essential medicines within health systems (World Health Organization 2021).

However, the qualitative findings indicate that sustainable compliance cannot rely solely on administrative enforcement and individual accountability but requires robust health information systems that enable real-time monitoring, prescribing guidance, and decision support. Electronic prescribing systems and computerized clinical decision support tools have been shown to significantly improve prescribing accuracy, reduce medication errors, and enhance compliance with formulary restrictions (Jia et al. 2016; Scott et al. 2018; Baysari and Raban 2019). Integration of formulary restriction criteria into electronic prescribing workflows enables automated verification, improves prescribing transparency, and strengthens medication safety (Ford et al. 2021; Cahill et al. 2025).

From a policy perspective, this study highlights the importance of adopting balanced formulary restriction strategies that combine governance oversight with clinical flexibility. Evidence suggests that formulary implementation supported by adaptive health system design, clinician engagement, and integrated digital infrastructure improves prescribing behavior and supports sustainable compliance (Kanai et al. 2022; Nazar et al. 2023). Digital integration also supports audit–feedback mechanisms, which are critical components of effective pharmaceutical governance and rational drug use policies (Zairina et al. 2024).

From an educational perspective, the integration of National Formulary information into clinical dashboards and electronic prescribing systems has important implications for professional development and continuous learning. Clinical decision support systems provide real-time guidance and reinforce evidence-based prescribing practices, helping healthcare professionals align clinical decisions with formulary policies and patient safety standards (Jia et al. 2016; Scott et al. 2018). These systems also function as embedded educational tools, supporting rational prescribing behavior and strengthening clinical decision-making capacity (Ford et al. 2021).

Strengthening interoperability between formulary databases and hospital information systems is essential to ensure sustainable formulary governance, prescribing transparency, and medication safety. Evidence indicates that integrated electronic prescribing systems improve compliance with prescribing guidelines, reduce prescribing errors, and enhance overall healthcare system efficiency (Baysari and Raban 2019; Cahill et al. 2025). Aligning technological innovation, pharmaceutical policy, and professional education is therefore critical to sustaining rational drug use and improving healthcare quality and patient safety within national health systems (Peacocke et al. 2022).

Implications for public health and education

The findings of this study carry important implications for both public health practice and health professional education, particularly in the context of strengthening rational drug use within national health insurance systems. At the public health level, the high compliance with National Formulary restrictions observed in this study demonstrates the potential effectiveness of formulary policies as instruments for cost containment, quality assurance, and medication safety when supported by strong institutional commitment and appropriate governance structures. However, the qualitative findings indicate that sustainable compliance cannot rely solely on administrative enforcement and individual accountability. Instead, it requires robust health information systems that enable real-time monitoring, feedback, and documentation of clinical decision-making. Strengthening digital infrastructure and integrating formulary restrictions into electronic prescribing systems should therefore be prioritized as part of broader health system strengthening efforts to ensure equitable, efficient, and safe access to medicines (Holloway et al. 2020).

From a policy perspective, this study highlights the importance of adopting a balanced approach to formulary restriction implementation. Systems that are overly rigid may provoke resistance from prescribers and inadvertently undermine adherence, whereas recommendatory and flexible digital systems can preserve professional autonomy while maintaining transparency and accountability. Such an approach aligns with contemporary public health strategies

that emphasize adaptive governance, clinician engagement, and the use of health information technology to support evidence-based decision-making (Carli et al. 2018).

In terms of education, the integration of National Formulary information into clinical dashboards and prescribing workflows has significant implications for the continuous professional development of healthcare providers. Real-time audit and feedback mechanisms function not only as administrative controls but also as embedded learning tools that reinforce evidence-based prescribing and medication safety principles in daily clinical practice. This underscores the need for pharmacy, medical, and interprofessional education curricula to place greater emphasis on health informatics, rational drug use policies, and the ethical dimensions of formulary compliance. Training future healthcare professionals to navigate digital decision-support systems, interpret formulary guidance, and justify clinical deviations appropriately is essential to sustaining rational prescribing behaviors. Collectively, these implications suggest that strengthening formulary adherence should be viewed as a shared responsibility across public health policy, health system design, and professional education. By aligning technological innovation, regulatory frameworks, and educational strategies, health systems can promote sustainable compliance with National Formularies while safeguarding patient safety and quality of care (Baysari and Raban 2019). Digital formulary integration can enable real-time prescribing guidance, automated alerts, and audit–feedback mechanisms, improving prescribing transparency, rational drug use, and healthcare system efficiency. Strengthening interoperability between formulary databases and hospital information systems is essential to ensure sustainable formulary governance.

Strengths and limitations of the study

This study has several important strengths. First, the use of a mixed-methods design enabled a comprehensive evaluation of National Formulary restriction implementation by integrating quantitative measurement of prescribing compliance with qualitative exploration of underlying system-level, organizational, and behavioral determinants. This approach provided both objective compliance data and contextual insights into factors influencing formulary adherence. Second, the large prescription dataset analyzed in the quantitative phase enhances the robustness and reliability of the compliance findings. Third, the qualitative analysis provided in-depth insights into digital infrastructure, governance mechanisms, and workflow-related factors, whereas the development of a project map offers a practical framework to support future formulary implementation and health system improvement.

Nevertheless, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, this study was conducted in a single tertiary referral hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings, particularly primary care facilities or hospitals with different levels of digital infrastructure and institutional capacity. Second, the qual-

itative component involved a limited number of key informants, and although data saturation was achieved, the findings may not fully represent the perspectives of all relevant stakeholders. Third, this study primarily assessed formulary compliance and implementation processes but did not evaluate downstream clinical, economic, or patient safety outcomes associated with formulary adherence. Finally, as the study was cross-sectional in nature, it did not assess temporal changes in prescribing behavior or the long-term impact of potential system improvements. Future multicenter and longitudinal studies are therefore needed to validate the findings and assess the sustainability and broader impact of formulary implementation strategies.

Future direction

Future research should extend these findings by examining the long-term clinical, economic, and safety outcomes associated with sustained compliance with National Formulary restrictions. Longitudinal studies evaluating changes in prescribing behavior, medication safety, and healthcare costs following implementation of digital formulary support systems would provide valuable evidence on the effectiveness and sustainability of formulary governance interventions. Multicenter studies involving hospitals with varying levels of digital maturity and institutional capacity are also needed to assess the scalability and generalizability of formulary implementation strategies across different healthcare settings. Such studies would help identify system-level and organizational factors that influence successful integration of formulary decision support systems into routine clinical workflows.

In addition, prospective research evaluating the impact of advanced clinical decision support features such as automated formulary alerts, prescriber authorization verification, adaptive prescribing recommendations, and integration with pharmacovigilance systems would provide important insights into optimizing formulary compliance while maintaining clinical flexibility and patient-centered care.

Future studies should also explore the role of targeted educational interventions, interprofessional collaboration, and digital health literacy in improving prescriber engagement and acceptance of formulary policies. Integrating digital innovation with continuous professional development and health system strengthening efforts may help support more resilient, efficient, and sustainable formulary systems that promote rational drug use and improve healthcare quality.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates high compliance with National Formulary restrictions in a tertiary hospital setting, supported by effective institutional governance and prescribing oversight. However, the sustainability of formulary adherence remains dependent on strengthening digital integration, automated monitoring, and clinical decision

support systems. Enhancing digital formulary infrastructure and integrating decision support tools into routine prescribing workflows are essential to promote rational drug use, improve medication safety, and ensure sustainable healthcare delivery within Indonesia's National Health Insurance system.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki regarding research involving human participants.

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The patients/participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

The authors confirm contributions to the paper as follows: study conception and design: EL, PP, MH; data collection: SF, MH, AC; analysis and interpretation of results: PP, AY, SS; draft manuscript preparation: EL, PP, MH, AK. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Elmiawati Latifah <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3328-3700>

Prasojo Pribadi <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7408-2924>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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